

**PREDICTION OF BOCCIA PLAYING ABILITY ON SELECTED
BIOMECHANICAL VARIABLES AMONG PERSONS WITH
CEREBRAL PALSY**

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Abstract:

The aim of the study is to predicting the playing ability of individuals with cerebral palsy in Boccia, a Paralympics sport designed for those with severe physical disabilities, involves an intricate examination of selected biomechanical variables. The angle of release and velocity of the ball have the high tendency to predict the playing ability of BOCCIA on selected biomechanical variables of persons with cerebral palsy. The relationship between the playing ability and angle of ball released and velocity of ball is possessing strong positive correlation, these variables, encompassing of movement, coordination and strength, play a pivotal role in determining a playing proficiency in the sport. To achieve the purpose of the study, thirty (N=30) persons with cerebral palsy (Wheel chaired) were selected as subjects from Anugraha Home for Cerebral Palsy, Coimbatore District, Tamilnadu. Their age ranges from 22 to 38 years and having at least two years of inmate of the home. The dependent variable is playing ability of BOCCIA game assessed by Coaches Rating. Static group research design is used to evaluate the pre-stated hypothesis, as it to predict the playing ability of BOCCIA on selected biomechanical variables of persons with cerebral palsy. Biomechanical variables were used to form respective linear predictive models (step-wise argument selection) with special reference to their playing ability. $P > 00.05$ was considered statistically significant. Out of three independent variable, angle of release & velocity of the ball were high contributing facts towards the playing ability of Boccia game among persons with cerebral palsy.

Key Words: Playing proficiency, Angle of ball release, Velocity of ball, BOCCIA and cerebral palsy.

Introduction:

Adaptive sports are competitive or recreational sports for people with disabilities. Adaptive sports often run parallel to typical sport activities (Angel-Lopez, et al., 2019). However, they allow modifications necessary for people with disabilities to participate and many sports use a classification system that puts athletes with physical challenges on an even playing field with each other (Fletcher, Gallinger & Prince, 2021). For instance athletes with hemiplegia competing in track events are usually classified T37. The T is for track (F37 is for field events), the 3 represents a cerebral palsy classification and the 7 specifies an athlete with weakness/spasticity on one side of the body (Cammidge, 2017). The use of a detailed classification system based on type of disability allows for a more fair competition. For events such as the National Junior Disability Championships (NJDC), qualifying standards are based on age and disability classification. From a seated position, players propel balls to land as close as possible to a white marker ball, known as the Jack. Two sides compete as individuals, pairs or as a team of three over a set number of ends (4 for individuals and pairs, and 6 for teams). Each side plays six balls (red or blue) each end. After each end, the athlete, pair or team with the ball closest to the jack receives 1 point plus an additional point for each ball closer to the jack than their opponent's. Points are accumulated over the course of a match to find a winner. Throwing distance and competitive performance of Boccia players (Kataoka2020) although simple to get started, the tactics of the sport offer both tension and excitement as the game plays out. Balls can be rolled down a ramp, thrown or kicked. Such as a head pointer. Predict the overall development of the sport; to aid in the optimization of training methodologies, and potentially enhance performance outcomes for BOCCIA athletes. The purpose of the study is to prediction of boccia on selected biomechanical characteristics and playing ability of BOCCIA among persons with cerebral palsy.

Methods:

Subjects:

The objective of the research study is to predict the playing ability of BOCCIA on selected biomechanical variables of persons with cerebral palsy. To achieve the purpose of the study, thirty (N=30) persons with cerebral palsy (Wheel chaired) were selected as subjects from Anugraha Home for Cerebral Palsy, Coimbatore District, Tamilnadu.

Procedures:

The procedure of the test was explained in simple language and demonstrate a few throw capturing techniques, proper placement of the tripods, and calibration with YI sports camera controlled by android mobile phones, before conduction of test to the subject. The trial has been practiced by the subjects for two throw as realistic as possible. Two cameras were controlled by two separated android mobile phones via Wi-Fi mode. By starting the on buttons on the two cameras simultaneously, the shooter will execute the 5 throw; at a stretch all the actions were recorded.

Table 1: Selection of Variables and Test Descriptions

Biomechanical Variables (Independent)	Unit of Measure	Test Description	Instrument Used
Elbow angle, Angle of ball release	Degree	Angle between the (digital and proximal) two bones on the respective joint	Kinovea Software with Y1 Sports Camera (Trial Version)
Velocity of ball	Meter / Second	The displacement of the ball when it is released from the hand and reached the target area (near as possible to jack ball) at the rate of seconds	
Throw for Accuracy	Points	The accuracy of the BOCCIA ball throws towards the jack or target ball	BOCCIA

Performance Evaluation:

Online open source of Kinovea software with Y1 Sports camera were used for the study and were periodically tested and checked the calibration. The calibrations were tested and found to be accurate enough to serve the purpose of the study. Kinovea Software with two Y1 sports camera fixed in tripods controlled by two android mobile phones. On the starting line, extended one meter away laterally from the end line, one Y1 Sports Camera was fixed at the height of 5 meter above the floor to record the lateral portion of the Jack-ball throw shooter. Totally 5 throws were given to the players each ball having minimum of 1 point and maximum of 6 points according to the placement of the thrown ball nearest to the Jack-ball. By this way, performance of the player were evaluated for 30 points. The angle of ball released, elbow angle, velocity of the ball were extracted by the video clips recorded during the execution of the wheel chaired Boccia player with cerebral palsy through Kinovea software.

Statistical Analysis:

Static group research design is used to evaluate the pre-stated hypothesis, as it to predict the playing ability of BOCCIA on selected biomechanical variables of persons with cerebral palsy. To achieve the purpose of the study, thirty (N=30) persons with cerebral palsy (Wheel chaired) were selected as subjects from Anugraha Home for Cerebral Palsy, Coimbatore District, Tamilnadu. The Statistical techniques included descriptive statistics, were applied. Biomechanical variables were used to form respective linear predictive models (step-wise argument selection) with special reference to their playing ability. $P > 00.05$ was considered to be statistically significant. The data were analyzed using statistical package SPSS 21st version.

Results of Descriptive Statistics:

The table 2 shows the minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation of the respective playing ability and biomechanical variables. The table 2, from their relationship, step-wise regression model was duplicated.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on Selected Biomechanical Variables of BOCCIA game among the Cerebral Palsy (N = 30)

Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Playing Ability	14	26	19.32	3.430
Elbow Angle	148	164	155.87	3.110
Angle of Release	26	54	43.94	6.378
Velocity of the Ball	0	4	2.05	1.199

From the table 2, it was clearly revealed that the maximum possible playing ability points will be 30 points (each ball maximum of 6 and for 5 throws) and the mean value falls very close to maximal point that indicates the cerebral palsy persons were played the BOCCIA game very well. The optimal angle for throw is 45 degree and the table shows the mean value of 43 degree (appx) ensured they are very sound in throwing the BOCCIA ball towards the Jack Ball.

Table 3: Multiple Correlation between Selected Biomechanical Variables and Playing Ability of BOCCIA game among the Cerebral Palsy (N = 30)

Variables	Playing Ability	Elbow Angle	Angle of Release	Velocity of the Ball
Playing Ability	1	.394	.800*	.785*
Elbow Angle		1	.467	.181
Angle of Release			1	.469
Velocity of the Ball				1

*significant at 0.05 level

From the above table 3, the relationship between the angle of release and Playing ability ($r = 0.80$) and Playing ability versus velocity of the ball ($r = 0.79$) were possessing significant high positive correlation among the persons with cerebral palsy playing the game BOCCIA.

Table 4: Step-wise Regression Model for Selected Biomechanical Variables towards Playing Ability of BOCCIA game among the Cerebral Palsy (N = 30)

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.800 ^a	.641	.628	2.06167		
2	.925 ^b	.855	.845	1.33210		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Angle of Ball Release						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Angle of Ball Release, Velocity of the Ball						
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.674	2.677		.252	.803
	Angle of Ball Release	.426	.060	.800	7.065	.000
2	(Constant)	3.469	1.785		1.943	.062
	Angle of Ball Release	.295	.044	.554	6.689	.000
	Velocity of the Ball	1.457	.230	.525	6.330	.000
a. Dependent Variable: VAR00001						

Table 4 shows the regression analyses for playing ability of BOCCIA game among cerebral palsy in the sample. Among the biomechanical variables, angle of ball release scores accounted for 80 % in the first model of the playing ability. The velocity of the ball subsequently added significantly (0.01, and 0.05) in the final model and accounted for 92% with R Square change 24% ($\Delta R^2 = 0.86$).

$$\text{Playing Ability} = 3.469 + (\text{Angle of Ball Release}) * 0.295 + (\text{Velocity of the Ball}) * 1.457.$$

Discussion on Findings:

The relationship between the playing ability and angle of ball released and velocity of ball is posing strong positive correlation. Throwing balls requires upper extremity and torso coordination that were greatly influenced by velocity of the ball and its released angle. Since placement of the Boccia Ball very close to the Jack-ball determines the success and failure of the game, precision control over the ball was highly required on the player’s counterpart. Monitoring elderly while playing Boccia game play (Arezes 2017). Playing the game with cerebral palsy, really requires control over the force given during the ball throw towards the jack-ball. Particularly, the velocity of the ball thrown and the released angle were crucial key factors that decides the points of the each thrown ball (Chan2012). Upper limb muscle fatigue during prolonged Boccia games with underarm throwing technique. Sometimes the movement preferred by the coaches and trainers, may cause high risk of worsening further injury (Doewes, Elumalai & Azmi (2023), demands precaution measures to prevent it. For achieving the greatest level of athletic ability and minimizing the risk of injury, adaptive technology used in Paralympics sports with a special focus on wheeled technology has to be given due importance in implementing game specific training. Development of Boccia Cerebral Palsy's National Athlete Achievement in the Indonesian National Paralympic Committee (Haris 2020). Individual difference were significantly differ regarding the distance between a thrown ball and a target ball (jack) that’s because of the level of cerebral injury differed from individual to individual. The result of the study stated that the biomechanical variables of the players were contributed significantly towards the playing ability, specifically, angle of ball released and velocity of the ball, were in accordance with Huang, Pan, Ou, Yu, & Tsai, (2014); Cooper & De Luigi (2014).

Conclusions:

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn.

- The angle of release and velocity of the ball have the high tendency to predict the playing ability of BOCCIA on selected biomechanical variables of persons with cerebral palsy.
- The relationship between the playing ability and angle of ball released and velocity of ball is posing strong positive correlation.

Practical Applications:

Boccia is a precision ball sport that requires athletes to throw or roll balls towards a target, and biomechanical analysis can provide insights into various aspects of the game. Biomechanical variables play a crucial role in enhancing performance and understanding the mechanics of movements in sports Boccia. Overall biomechanical analysis plays a important role in enhancing performance, preventing injuries, and optimizing training strategies in Boccia. By analyzing biomechanical variables, coaches and sports scientists can identify movement patterns that may increase the risk of injury in Boccia players. This information can be used to design training programs that focus on improving biomechanical efficiency and reducing the likelihood of injuries. By leveraging biomechanical data, coaches and athletes

can gain valuable insights that can lead to improved performance on the court. The result of the study will add a quantum of knowledge in the sports discipline specifically in the game Boccia, players with cerebral palsy.

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